

Effects of different types of feeds on growth and survival of *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Boone, 1931)

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ABSTRACT

In the present study, effect of different animal feed levels on water quality, growth performance and proximate composition of Pacific white shrimp Litopenaeus vannamei has been investigated. The major water quality parameters like temperature, salinity, pH, dissolved oxygen, ammonia and nitrite were recorded by standard measurements. The present study results showed that fresh feed experimentally cultured a prominent role in maintaining good water quality parameters throughout the culture period. The significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher survival and growth indices was observed in polychaete feed when compared to the other feed and control. Significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher protein, lipid and carbohydrate was recorded in clam and polychaete feed. Significantly lower protein and lipid content was recorded in trash fish feed. Furthermore, lower carbohydrate was recorded in clam fed shrimp. Among the above feeds, the polychaete feed showed the better growth performance and survival rate.

KEYWORDS: Pacific white shrimp, different feeds, water quality, growth, proximate composition.

1. INTRODUCTION

White leg shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei* Boone, 1931), native of Central American waters, is the most important aquaculture shrimp species in the world (Carvalho and Nunes, 2006; Rosenberry, 2000). White leg shrimp was introduced as an aquaculture species in Asia and especially China during mid-year 1990 (Sakthivel et al., 20214). At present, white leg shrimp culture involves major contribution of shrimp culture in

the world. Compared to other shrimp species the white shrimp *Litopenaeus vannamei* is the dominant species cultured worldwide. The Pacific white shrimp (*L. vannamei*) is one of the most economically important marine aquaculture species and is the most produced shrimp species in the world (FAO, 2016; <http://www.fao.org/fishery/en>). The *L. vannamei* is the most widely cultured shrimp species in the western hemisphere where this particular species contributes to

about 90% of the total shrimp culture (Wurmann *et al.*, 2004). According to Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO) report (2009), the shrimp is the largest sea food commodity around the world, which occupies 17 % of all the international trade, in which about 75 % of production is from aquaculture constituted by two candidate species, namely *L. vannamei* and *Penaeus monodon*. The introduced species *L. vannamei* is now completely overtaking regional shrimp production that was dominated before by the native shrimp, *P. monodon* (FAO, 2017).

Valued at over US\$16.6 billion, global farmed shrimp production was estimated at nearly 3.78 million tons in 2010, with production increasing over three-fold from 1.1 million tons in 2000, and growing at an average annual rate of 14.5 percent since 1950 (FAO, 2012). Moreover, the white leg shrimp (*L. vannamei*) was ranked first in 2010 in terms of total farmed fish and crustacean production by value, at US\$11.23 billion (FAO, 2012).

In 2010, the world aquaculture production of crustaceans consisted of freshwater species (29.4 %) and marine species (70.6 %). *L. vannamei* is the most successful marine species for aquaculture. It accounted for 71.8 % of world production of all farmed marine shrimp species, of which 77.9 % was produced in Asia (FAO, 2012 & 2018). This would not have been possible if not for the controlled introduction of in *L. vannamei* as per the risk assessment study carried out by Central Institute of Brackishwater Aquaculture (CIBA) and National Bureau of Fish Genetic Resources (NBFGR) and the quarantine center for *L. vannamei* brood stock operated by Rajiv Gandhi Center for Aquaculture (RGCA). The white shrimp *L. vannamei* is the dominant shrimp species currently cultured worldwide (FAO, 2011).

Feed management plays a key role in enhancing the production of aquatic species. The most important goals of sustainable aquaculture are to create a system that reduces the need for non-renewable resources in the nature (Ahamod *et al.*, 2016). High-density production/biofloc technology (BFT), which is environmentally friendly and can be useful for development of sustainable aquaculture through intensive fish production by recycling of water (Khanjani and Sharifinia, 2020).

Artificial (pellet and frozen) feed decays rapidly and easily deteriorates water quality (Sheen and Wu, 1999). But, pellet diet offers many advantages compared to fresh feed, which includes stability, shelf life, reliable supply, minimal preparation time and known nutrient content. Natural food or live food plays a very important role in aquaculture, especially in rearing and improved extensive culture systems. Live food includes algae, zooplankton (rotifers, water flea, copepods) and benthos (oligochaetes, polychaetes, mollusks, small crustaceans). The adequate production of natural feed can contribute to enhancing the economic feasibility of shrimp culture between 25% and 85% (Martinez-Cordova *et al.*, 1998). In the aquatic environment the natural feed can be stimulated by adding organic or inorganic fertilizers to increasing the availability of nutrients and productivity (Hansen *et al.*, 2003 and Chithra *et al.*, 2016).

Live feeds like clam meat, polychaetes (*Perenereis nuntia*), squids, other mollusks, *Artemia* biomass and rotifers are preferred over commercial feeds, even though they are costly, have high amount of polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) and maximum efficacy in terms of growth and survival. The present study was undertaken to determine the effects of live feed (*Neries* sp.) and pellet feeds on the growth and survival of early juveniles of *L. vannamei*.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Study area

The culture work was conducted in the fish hatchery laboratory of CAS in Marine Biology, Faculty of Marine Science, Annamalai University. The culture experiment conducted for 90 days from November 2018 to April 2019.

2.2. Experimental animal

The *L. vannamei* juveniles were procured from Rajiv Gandhi Centre for Aquaculture (RGCA, Thoduvai). Juveniles were packed in double plastic bags filled with oxygen and water in the ratio of 3:1 in each bag and the density of shrimp was 100/bag. The number of juveniles to be packed in oxygen inflated polythene bags was calculated as per the formula of Jameson *et al.* (1995).

Settings of experimental tanks and live feed

The experiment was conducted in four sets of experimental (250 L FRP) tanks. Each experimental set has four numbers of tanks. Based on the feeding type

the four sets of tanks were placed and maintained in a protected place (Fig. 1).

Experimental tank Set No.1: Control (Pellet feed)

Experimental tank Set No.2: Polychaete (*Nereis* sp.)

Experimental tank Set No.3: Trash fish (*Sardinella longiceps*)

Experimental tank Set No.4: Clam (*Meretrix meretrix*)

The polychaete (*Nereis* sp.), clam (*M. meretrix*) and trash fish (*S. longiceps*) were procured fresh from the local fishermen.

units received 10 % water exchange daily and 100 % exchange of water on weekends

Water quality parameters such as temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen, pH, nitrite, and ammonia were measured *in-situ* condition by following the methods described in APHA (American Public Health Association, 1998). The temperature was measured by using a standard Celsius thermometer. The salinity was measured by using hand refractometer (ATAGO,

2. 3. Culture and Maintenance

The *L. vannamei* were stocked in four 250 L FRP and each tank were stocked at the rate of 15 number of shrimps per tank. Acclimatization was carried out over 4 weeks. During the study the experimental tanks were maintained aeration using 2 air stone-hoses type of diffuser system which is fitted to 2 HP blowers. All the experimental

Japan). Dissolved oxygen was estimated by using Winkler's method as described (Strickland and Parsons, 1972). The pH was measured using pH pen (Eutech, Model-Ecophtesti). The nitrite content of samples were analysed by following the method described by Strickland and Parsons (1972). Ammonia concentration was estimated by following the method suggested by Grasshoff *et al.* (1983).

Fig. 1: Feed formulation four different concentration sets of experimental tanks in (a) Pellet feed (b) Polychaete, (c) Clam and (d) Trash fish supplemented tanks

2. 4. Proximate Composition of live feeds

Moisture and ash content was estimated by following the method described in (Association of Official Analytical Chemists, AOAC) Horwitz *et al.* (1990). Protein was estimated by the method of Lowry *et al.* (1951); Total carbohydrate by Carroll *et al.* (1956); Total lipid was estimated by the method of Barnes and Blackstock (1973) and Fatty acids profile was estimated by following Annon (2000) and Sahin *et al.* (2000).

2. 5. Feeding experiment

One control tank was maintained and the shrimps in this tank were fed with commercial pellet feed on the growth performance of white shrimp, *L. vannamei*. The growth performance (final body weight, weight gain and specific growth rate) and survival rate of the shrimps fed with fresh feeds was compared to the commercial pellet feed fed control shrimps. Dead shrimps were immediately removed. A random sample of 15 shrimps/ tank was measured to estimate the growth parameters at every 30 days. Shrimp were fed with one of these four diets at 6 % of total body weight

daily. During the rearing experiment (90 days), feeds were given three times/ day respectively.

2. 6. Evaluation of growth performance parameters

At the end of the feeding experiment, growth parameters such as body weight gain, body length gain (from postorbital edge to tip of telson), body weight, daily growth rate, specific growth rate, feed conversion ratio and survival were measured every week. Shrimp weight was measured on a weekly basis to determine shrimp growth and the amount of feed and organic carbon offered. Growth parameters were determined based on the following equations (Tacon *et al.*, 2002; Khanjani *et al.*, 2016 and Khanjani *et al.*, 2020).

Body weight gain (gm) = final weight - initial weight

Body length gain (cm) = final length - initial length

Survival rate (%) = (number of individuals at the end of testing period/initial number of individuals stocked) × 100.

Specific growth rate (SGR in Weight) (%/day) = $[(\ln \text{ final length} - \ln \text{ initial length}) / \text{rearing duration in days}] \times 100$

Feed conversion ratio (FCR) = total feed intake/ total biomass gain

For biochemical studies the dried meat was powdered and the required quantity was used for protein, lipid, carbohydrate and fatty acids determination

2. 7. Statistical analysis

Mean ± standard error (S.E) was calculated for weight, length and indexes. Data were analyzed using one-way analysis of variance ($p < 0.05$). Mean differences were compared by Duncan's multiple range tests at the level of 0.05. Dependent variables included survival, growth, and biomass; independent variables evaluated included temperature, salinity, DO, pH, nitrite and ammonia concentrations, as well as conductivity, alkalinity, and pH values. All data represent the pooled counts from three replicates per tanks.

3. RESULTS

3. 1. Physico-chemical parameters

During the experimental work, there were no significant differences between water quality variables, except for water temperature maximum was recorded in clam and polychaete fed shrimp tank (26.0°C) and the minimum was recorded in control and trash fish fed shrimp tank (25.0°C). The maximum water salinity was

recorded in clam (26 ppt) fed shrimp tank and the minimum was recorded in polychaete (25 ppt) fed shrimp tank. The maximum water pH was recorded in polychaete and clam fed shrimp tank (7.9) and the minimum was recorded in control and trash fish fed shrimp tank (7.8). The maximum dissolved oxygen level was recorded in polychaete fed shrimp tank (4.8 mg/l) and minimum was recorded in trash fish fed shrimp tank (4.5 mg/l). The maximum ammonia level was recorded in control tank (0.14 μmol/l) and the minimum was recorded in polychaete fed shrimp tank 0.12 μmol/l. The maximum nitrite level was recorded in control tank (0.32 μmol/l) and the minimum was recorded in polychaete fed shrimp tank (0.22 μmol/l) (Table 1).

3. 2. Length and weight gain

The maximum length of the experimentally cultured shrimps was recorded in polychaete fed shrimp tank (12.3 cm) and the minimum was recorded in control tank (8.4 cm). The maximum weight of the experimentally cultured shrimps was recorded in Polychaete fed shrimp tank (12.5 g) and the minimum was recorded in control tank (5.9 g).

3. 2. Growth indices

The maximum survival of the experimentally cultured shrimps was recorded in polychaete fed shrimp tank (90.0%) and the minimum was recorded in trash fish fed shrimp tank (73.3%). The maximum (BLG) body length gain of the experimentally cultured shrimps was recorded in polychaete fed shrimp tank (8.3cm) and the minimum was recorded in control tank (4.5cm). The maximum (BWG) body weight gain of the experimentally cultured shrimps was recorded in polychaete fed shrimp tank (10.5g) and the minimum was recorded in control tank (5.9g). The maximum (SGR) specific growth rate of the experimentally cultured shrimps was recorded in polychaete fed shrimp tank (1.01 %/day) and the minimum was recorded in control tank (0.72 %/day). The maximum (FCR) feed conversion ratio of the experimentally cultured shrimps was recorded in control tank (2.54) and the minimum was recorded in polychaete fed shrimp tank (1.30) (Table 2).

3. 3. Proximate composition

The maximum protein of the experimentally cultured shrimps was recorded in clam fed shrimp tank (52.71 %)

and the minimum was recorded in trash fish fed shrimp tank (36.71 %). The maximum lipid of the experimentally cultured shrimps was recorded in polychaete fed shrimp tank (21.28 %) and the minimum was recorded in trash fish fed shrimp tank (12.83 %). The maximum carbohydrate of the experimentally polychaete fed shrimp tank (2.46 %). The maximum ash of the experimentally cultured shrimps was recorded trash fish fed shrimp tank (21.14 %) and the minimum was recorded in polychaete fed shrimp tank (13.86 %) (Table 3).

3. 4. Fatty acid accumulation in fresh feed

This study evaluated the accumulation of fatty acids in fresh feed, focusing on total saturated fatty acids (SFA), monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFA), and polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) across different

cultured shrimps was recorded in trash fish fed shrimp tank (16.37 %) and the minimum was recorded in clam fed shrimp tank (9.86 %). The maximum moisture of the experimentally cultured shrimps was recorded in trash fish fed shrimp tank (13.15 %) and the minimum was recorded in feed types: polychaete, clam, trash fish, and a control sample. The fatty acid profiles of each feed type are summarized in Table 4. The total SFA content was highest in the control sample (34.36%), followed by trash fish (32.72%), clam (28.52%), and polychaete (21.38%). For MUFA, trash fish had the highest content (54.80%), followed by clam (50.10%), control (50.02%), and polychaete (35.44%). The highest PUFA content was found in polychaete (43.18%), with clam (21.38%), control (15.62%), and trash fish (12.48%) showing lower levels.

Table 1: Water quality parameters (mean ± SD) in variation experiment of *L. vannamei*

Water quality parameters	Control	Polychaete	Trash fish	Clam
Temperature (°C)	25 ± 1.24 ^{ab}	26 ± 1.64 ^a	25 ± 1.04 ^{ab}	26 ± 0.98 ^a
Salinity (ppt)	25.5 ± 0.58 ^{ab}	25.0 ± 0.73 ^c	25.5 ± 0.60 ^{ab}	26 ± 0.85 ^a
Water pH	7.8 ± 0.86 ^{ab}	7.9 ± 0.69 ^a	7.8 ± 0.83 ^{ab}	7.9 ± 0.74 ^a
Dissolve Oxygen (mg/l)	4.7 ± 0.53 ^b	4.8 ± 0.58 ^a	4.5 ± 0.52 ^d	4.6 ± 0.62 ^c
Ammonium (µmol/l)	0.14 ± 0.06 ^a	0.12 ± 0.03 ^c	0.13 ± 0.04 ^{ab}	0.13 ± 0.04 ^{ab}
Nitrite (µmol/l)	0.32 ± 0.13 ^a	0.22 ± 0.08 ^d	0.30 ± 0.01 ^b	0.26 ± 0.09 ^c

Table 2: Evaluation of growth performance (mean ± SD) of *L. vannamei* fed an different animal feeds

Growth performance	Control	Polychaete	Clam	Trash fish
Survival (%)	76.6 ± 0.57 ^c	90.0 ± 0.87 ^a	83.3 ± 0.74 ^b	73.3 ± 0.65 ^d
Initial length	3.9 ± 0.38 ^{ab}	4.0 ± 0.42 ^a	4.0 ± 0.36 ^a	4.0 ± 0.45 ^a
Final length	8.4 ± 0.69 ^d	12.3 ± 0.68 ^a	9.8 ± 0.52 ^b	8.8 ± 0.62 ^c
LG (cm)	4.5 ± 0.75 ^d	8.3 ± 0.76 ^a	5.8 ± 0.58 ^b	4.9 ± 0.84 ^c
Initial weight	2.05 ± 0.09 ^c	2.0 ± 0.18 ^d	2.15 ± 0.14 ^a	2.1 ± 0.31 ^b
Final weight	7.95 ± 0.24 ^d	12.5 ± 0.39 ^a	9.45 ± 0.47 ^b	8.6 ± 0.28 ^c
WG (g)	5.9 ± 0.74 ^d	10.5 ± 0.95 ^a	7.3 ± 0.84 ^b	6.5 ± 0.62 ^c
SGR (%/day)	0.72 ± 0.36 ^d	1.01 ± 0.21 ^a	0.87 ± 0.46 ^b	0.76 ± 0.28 ^c
FCR	2.54 ± 0.22 ^a	1.30 ± 0.18 ^d	2.05 ± 0.21 ^c	2.29 ± 0.16 ^b

Table 3: Proximate composition of *L. vannamei* fed with animal feeds

Proximate composition	Protein (%)	Lipids (%)	Carbohydrate (%)	Moisture (%)	Ash (%)
Control	39.46 ± 0.42 ^c	13.80 ± 0.53 ^c	16.04 ± 0.31 ^b	11.69 ± 0.86 ^a	19.07 ± 0.47 ^b
Polychaete	48.32 ± 0.35 ^b	21.28 ± 1.03 ^a	14.08 ± 0.87 ^c	2.46 ± 0.42 ^d	13.86 ± 0.36 ^d
Clam	52.71 ± 1.02 ^a	16.36 ± 0.98 ^b	9.68 ± 0.53 ^d	4.58 ± 1.37 ^c	16.67 ± 0.38 ^c
Trash fish	36.51 ± 0.95 ^d	12.83 ± 0.41 ^d	16.37 ± 0.47 ^a	13.15 ± 1.83 ^b	21.14 ± 0.05 ^a

Table 4: Comparison of percentage composition of fatty acid profile between fresh feed

Carbon chain	Polychaete	Clam	Trash fish	Control
Total SFA	21.38	28.52	32.72	34.36
Total MUFA	35.44	50.10	54.80	50.02
Total PUFA	43.18	21.38	12.48	15.62

4. DISCUSSION

Shrimps are omnivorous detritus feeders and they prefer natural animal feed over the pellet feed. Growth rate in shrimp is influenced by the quality of feed. Generally, growth performance depends on the feed digestibility, its energy content and on its composition (Pina *et al.*, 2006). Obviously, at younger stage, shrimps assimilate nutrients more efficiently than the older individuals. In addition to the type of food, the physiological efficiency, utilization and assimilation of diets also influence the growth of shrimps (Yong *et al.*, 2004). Biosecurity and costs are the two elements frequently associated with the need to reduce water exchange. Semi-intensive shrimp cultivation systems use 5% to 20% water exchange per day (FAO, 2006) to maintain acceptable water quality, mainly because they lack artificial aeration to support carrying capacity.

In the present study, the range of water quality parameters values was maintained within the passible level. Boyd and Gautier (2000) reported that water quality parameters wise, temperature, dissolved oxygen, salinity, pH, total ammonia nitrogen and nitrite nitrogen are the experimental in *L. vannamei* farm. Temperature, dissolved oxygen, salinity, pH, ammonia and nitrite showed low variation during the experimental period. Temperature was measured between 24.5 to 26°C and salinity at 25 and 28 ppt. Levels of dissolved oxygen (4.1 to 4.6mg/l), pH (7.9 to 8.3), ammonium (0.09 to 2.0µmol/l) and nitrite (0.22 to 0.44µmol/l) were found optimal throughout the experimental period.

The highest survival was observed in polychaete fed shrimps followed by clam meat and pellet fed shrimps. Similar findings were recorded by Meenakshi *et al.* (1970) *Fenneropenaeus merguensis* in the present study has shown variation in the survival rate of shrimps fed with live and pellet diet. However, in the present study the shrimps fed with animal diets have shown the

highest weight gain and survival compared to those fed with the pellet feed.

In the present study, maximum weight gain and length gain and SGR were recorded in shrimps grown with polychaete feed but showed significant differences with control tank. Similarly, Murugesan *et al.* (2011) reported higher weight gain and length gain in polychaete fed clown fish, *Amphiprion sebae*. Many of previous studies have shown that *L. vannamei* grown in biofloc system can improve shrimp survival and growth as compared to clear water (Cohen *et al.*, 2005; Wasielesky *et al.*, 2006; Mishra *et al.*, 2008 and Kim *et al.*, 2014). Growth in all treatment groups except for the polychaetes fed with a mix of molt waste sludge and shellfish diet was higher than in natural populations (Chambers and Milne, 1975; Kristensen, 1984; Vedel and Riisgård, 1993). The highest weight gain, length gain and SGR were obtained in BFT1 but showed no significant differences with other biofloc treatments. The highest survival was observed in BFT4 treatment. The highest FCR were obtained in the control (Khanjani *et al.*, 2016). Successful culture of *L. vannamei* on polychaetes based diets will ultimately ensure economic sustainability of mariculture venture through improved production.

In the present study, the effect of feeding different diets on proximate composition and hydrological entities in the *L. vannamei* of polychaete (*Neries* sp.), clam (*M. meretrix*), trash fish (*S. longiceps*) and Pellet feed was tested. Of this, polychaete could serve as a dietary source of protein and lipid as well as essential marine fatty acids and amino acids in feed for carnivorous fish and crustaceans, thus constituting a feed loop (Bischoff *et al.*, 2009 and Abbaszadeh *et al.*, 2019). Protein and lipid contents in polychaetes was comparable to those of fish feed and well within the recommended values for marine fish (Creswell, 1993; National Research Council, 2011). The significantly

higher protein, carbohydrate, lipids, moisture and ash content was observed in live polychaete feed fed clown fish, *Amphiprion sebae* (Murugesan *et al.*, 2011). The subsequent goal was to create a high-value product that can be further used as a resource for shrimp feed. It was shown that polychaetes could survive and grow when fed on molt waste sludge as a single food source. Moreover, they were able to efficiently incorporate lipid and protein as well as fatty and amino acids from their diets.

The fatty acid profiles of different fresh feed types provide insights into their potential nutritional benefits for shrimp diets. The control sample had the highest saturated fatty acids (SFA) content, which may support energy density but could lead to excess energy storage rather than active growth. Trash fish, with the highest monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFA) content, is beneficial for energy utilization, potentially supporting better growth performance in shrimp. Importantly, polychaete stood out for its high polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) content, particularly valuable for shrimp health and growth due to PUFA's role in immune function and cell membrane integrity. These findings suggest that incorporating polychaete, calm and trash fish into shrimp feed could offer a balanced fatty acid profile to support stable growth and health.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the results presented in the current study revealed that polychaete fed shrimp showed significant influence of body biochemical composition followed by better growth performance water quality parameters and survival. Hence present study concluded that the polychaete fed shrimp for the sustainable culture. However, continues effect of animal feeds on shrimps needs to ascertain in further experiments.

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Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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